

MultiLab – Novel, configurable lab-on-chip platform for low-cost multipurpose diagnostics & environmental monitoring

There is an increasing need for miniaturised, **multifunctional sensors** providing simultaneous access to diverse chemical & biochemical information, required in various applications including point-of-care (POC) diagnostics, environmental monitoring, agri-food products safety evaluation, industrial process monitoring and more. Nowadays, centralized laboratories have employed analytical techniques such as liquid and gas chromatography, mass spectrometry, and light microscopy to obtain critical chemical and biochemical data across diverse applications. While these methods remain important when an immediate response is not necessary, easy-to-use, rapid point-of-need sensors that can be used by non-specialized personnel or even operate in a completely automated (unattended) manner could be significant promise in a diverse range of fields such as disease management or for the early detection of environmental threats.

Nanophotonic devices that precisely control light in subwavelength volumes and enhance light–matter interactions, have opened up new prospects for sensing applications, addressing the limitations of current analytical methods in terms of sensitivity, ease-of-use, and miniaturization. Nevertheless, there are challenges to tackle before being able to widely adopt such devices in real-world applications. The MultiLab project is determined to overcome them.

At the core of **MultiLab's innovation** is a modular multi-sensing chip (sensor) compatible with large-scale manufacturing techniques that will allow to simultaneously detect biological, chemical, microorganism and molecular targets for medical diagnostics & environmental monitoring. Important novelties are foreseen in all sensing modalities exploited in the MultiLab chip, while innovative biofunctionalization methods, exploiting material-independent chemistries for the modification of sensor surfaces and new microfluidic system designs are used to maximise performance and improve robustness. Since large amount of data is expected as an outcome of the novel sensing platform, advanced approaches for computing, data processing and interpretation are also part of the project.

The versatility of the MultiLab platform will be showcased in two pivotal applications:

- a) **IoT-Enabled Early Warning of Harmful Algae Blooms (HAB):** Safeguarding freshwater sources with proactive monitoring of harmful algae blooms.
- b) **Diagnosis and Prognosis of Fever Without an Apparent Source:** Distinguishing between viral and bacterial origins for enhanced medical diagnostics.

The project is being coordinated by CyRIC, Cyprus Research and Innovation Center Ltd, in the framework of EU's Horizon Europe Programme. The project was launched on 1st January 2024 and will run for four years.

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Project partners include: CyRIC - Cyprus Research and Innovation Centre (Cyprus), Bialoom LTD (Cyprus), University of Ioannina (Greece) AMO GmbH (Germany), Multitel (Belgium), Servizo Galego de Saude (Spain), Buschjost GmbH (Germany), Technische Universität Wien (Austria), Aquamonitrix Limited (Ireland), DEEPLAB IKE (Greece) and Alpes Lasers SA (Switzerland).

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Notes for editors:

1. Horizon Europe is the biggest EU Research and Innovation programme ever with nearly €95.5 billion of funding available over 7 years (2021 to 2027) – in addition to the private investment that this money will attract. It promises more breakthroughs, discoveries, and world-firsts by taking great ideas from the lab to the market.

2. For media enquiries, please contact CyRIC on +357 22 777200 or e-mail info@cyric.eu

3. Project online presence:

Website: <https://multilab-project.eu/>

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/multilabproject/>

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Logos:

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